

INCREASES of ORGANIC CONTENTS OF SOILS THROUGH *Taloromyces funiculosus* APPLICATION

Un Akin^{1*}, Turkolmez Sahimerdan², Dervis Sibel² and Dikilitas Murat³

¹Soil, Fertilizer and Water Resources Central Research Institution, Ankara, Turkiye.

²GAP Agricultural Research Institution, Sanliurfa, Turkiye..

²Mardin Artuklu University, Kızıltepe High School, Department of Crop and Animal Production, Mardin, Turkiye

³Harran University, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Plant Protection, Şanlıurfa, Turkiye

* Presenting author: akin.un@tarimorman.gov.tr

ABSTRACT

Soil nutrient status tend to decrease gradually over the years even if fertilization is made. Inorganic and organic compounds tend to accumulate and lead to pollution if they are not decomposed. These compounds also increase the soil electrical conductivity (EC) level and pose a threat to crop plants especially in the seedling stages. In this study, over a 3-year period between 2021-2023, we applied *Taloromyces funiculosus* to the soils cultivated with barley or soybean as cover plants in winter seasons. We observed that total organic carbon (TOC) contents and soil organic matters (SOM) increased significantly over a 3-year period. The soils cultivated with barley or soybean without the fungus application exhibited a gradual increase in TOC and SOM contents. We evaluate that *T. funiculosus* has a significant role for improving and maintaining the soil chemical and physical properties. We are in the process of elucidating if the fungus acts as a biofertilizer due to possible synthesis of soil enzymes. But much more proof is needed in this area.

Keywords: *Taloromyces funiculosus*, total organic carbon, soil organic matters, barley, soybean.